

IMPORTANCE OF FAMILY EDUCATION - ISSUES OF GENDER QUALITY

¹Tursunmurad Mamatqabilov, ²Olim Yuldashev, ³Eshmuradov Dilshod

¹Academy of the Armed Forces of the Republic of Uzbekistan Department of National Pride and Military Patriotism associate professor

²Academy of the Armed Forces of the Republic of Uzbekistan lieutenant colonel

³Candidate of Technical Sciences, Tashkent University of Information Technologies

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8364160>

Abstract. This article provides information about the role of families in society and gender equality, as well as social relations, education and training.

Keywords: family, society, state, gender equality, education and upbringing.

In our country, where about eight million families live, the worldview of children is formed on the basis of the relationship between husband and wife. Their ideas about social life develop in accordance with their upbringing.

In this regard, as President Shavkat Mirziyoyev stated: "Our main goal will be to create all the opportunities for our children to fully realize their talents and abilities, noble aspirations, increase their social activity, take their rightful place in life." As you know, this year we introduced a new system to expand educational opportunities for our girls who grow up in low-income families. According to him, 940 additional places were allocated for such girls on the basis of a state grant this academic year in the daytime departments of higher educational institutions. [1]. Our work to protect the family, motherhood and childhood, the rights and interests of women, improve working and living conditions for women, and ensure legal equality are also consistently continuing. Of course, the reforms carried out in the field of education within the framework of the "Concept of Lifelong Spiritual Education" in our country, in turn, lay the foundation for the future development of our country. It is known from world development that education is one of the important aspects of society, it is a leading factor in the socialization and institutionalization of a person. The development of the education system in Uzbekistan is recognized as the main direction of the state's social policy. If we talk about the essence of the concept of legal equality and its significance in the development of society, then in legal terms, relations between women and men in all spheres of life and activity of society, in particular, in the fields of politics, economics, law, ideology and culture, education and science, It should be noted that this is an important social phenomenon. From this point of view, the legal concept not only represents the interests of women, but also means that both sexes should be given the same opportunity to boldly move towards their dreams and goals, improve the quality of life. [2]. One of the requirements of a developed society is to ensure equal rights for men and women. After all, this balance in society is the key to sustainable development and a prosperous future for mankind. Therefore, this value has enjoyed great respect in the history of human society since time immemorial. At the moment, if we look at the legal development of legal equality, in this respect it is necessary to specifically recognize the universal principles defined in the Universal Declaration of Human Rights adopted by the UN General Assembly in 1948. The Universal Declaration specifically recognizes the equality of men and women, and Article 1 of the Declaration states: "All human beings are born free and equal in dignity and rights. They have been given reason and conscience, so they should

treat each other in a spirit of brotherhood. Another international document adopted by the UN in 1966 is the International Covenant on Civil and Political Rights, in Article 3: “The States Parties to this Covenant undertake to ensure the equal enjoyment by men and women of all civil and political rights provided for in this Covenant”, - it was noted. Today, our independent country, which has ratified these international documents, attaches great importance to the issue of equality of women and men in its national legislation, based on the generally recognized requirements of international law. Especially in recent years, legal and practical work in this area has entered a new level. In recent years, two laws have been adopted regarding ensuring legal equality, supporting women, increasing their role in state and public administration, 6 resolutions and resolutions of the President, the government adopted 16 decisions. In particular, the Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan adopted on September 2, 2019 " On Guarantees of Equal Rights and Opportunities for Women and Men” is a comprehensive and basic legal document aimed at ensuring legal equality in our country. This law defines the concept of "legal" for the first time in our national legislation. The law determined the main directions of state policy in the field of ensuring equal rights and opportunities for women and men, as well as the mechanisms of state administration in this area. In particular, in order to prevent legal discrimination against women in the Republic of Uzbekistan, a commission on ensuring legal equality has been established. The advisory council on issues of legal equality in ministries and departments has been launched. It aims to ensure equal rights and opportunities for women and men in the political, social and economic spheres. At the heart of the resurgent reforms in Uzbekistan today, the focus is on improving the status of women in society, protecting their rights and opportunities as one of the priority values while ensuring the primacy of human interests. In particular, increasing the political, social and economic activity of women is being implemented as one of the priorities of state policy. It is important to note that over the next three years, important steps were taken to strengthen the legal and institutional framework for ensuring legal equality. Approximately 20 legal acts have been adopted, including 2 laws, 1 Decree of the President, 4 Decrees of the President, 13 resolutions of the Cabinet of Ministers aimed at protecting the rights and interests of women. An inventory of legislative documents was carried out in terms of compliance with the norms of labor and entrepreneurial rights of women. To date, in our country, in accordance with the Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan “On Guarantees of Equal Rights and Opportunities for Women and Men”, all ministries and departments have developed recommendations on the creation of bodies of the Advisory Council on Legal Equality. Advisory councils have been set up in trade unions. At the same time, it should be noted that in order to prevent discrimination against women in the Republic of Uzbekistan, a commission has been established to ensure legal equality. Today, by creating equal rights and opportunities for women and men in the social, economic and political spheres, factors for maintaining peace and economic stability are being created in our country. On the basis of this, a draft “Strategy for achieving legal equality in the Republic of Uzbekistan for 2020-2030” is being prepared and mutual cooperation with state and non-state organizations is widely distributed!

All directions provided in this strategy are developed in accordance with the UN Sustainable Development Goals until 2030.

Today, the leading young people of the new Uzbekistan are making unprecedented achievements in various fields, on a global scale, due to the purposeful and continuous upbringing of their parents. So, in the concept, upbringing and education cannot be separated from each other,

only when these two processes are organized on a harmonious, continuous basis, it is polite, has moral qualities, high spirituality, and at the same time is knowledgeable, intelligent, mentally and physically healthy, a broad worldview. and he talked about bringing up patriotic young people with a modern profession. At the same time, in the concept, the works carried out on the scientific and technological reform of youth education in Uzbekistan on a modern basis and its formation on the basis of scientific-based basic competencies and qualities based on the needs of today, increasing the effectiveness of continuous spiritual education, and turning it into the main factor of modern personnel training great importance is given [3].

The concept calls for a new, systematic approach to education, to fully reveal the socio-pedagogical possibilities of the family, pre-school education, general secondary, secondary special vocational, higher educational institutions, neighborhoods in the guaranteed formation of basic qualities in a child, and among them scientific-methodical sets the highest goal of raising unity to a new level.

Now, based on the requirements of the concept, systematic work is being carried out to raise the educational work in primary classes to meet today's requirements. At the same time, in this concept, special attention is paid to legal pedagogical opportunities in the educational system.

On August 23, 2020, the Oliy Majlis (Parliament) of the Republic of Uzbekistan adopted a new version of the Law "On Education". The law provides equal rights to education regardless of gender, language, age, race and nationality, faith, religion, social origin, profession, caste, place of residence, length of stay in the territory of the country.

The main principles of state policy in the field of education are:

- humanistic, democratic character of education and training; integrity and consistency of education;

- discretion in choosing directions of general secondary, as well as secondary special, professional education; equal access to education for all within the framework of state educational standards, etc. (Law on Education, Article 3).

As the main goal of the Concept - the gradual formation of social skills and qualities necessary for an independent and happy life in the young generation, in accordance with their age, it is envisaged to implement the following tasks in order to realize this goal:

- development of scientifically based indicators for evaluating spiritual and moral education;

- development and implementation of the methodology of education, starting from the period of pregnancy, based on the principles of gradualism and continuity;

- effective use of advanced achievements of national and modern pedagogy in the continuous education system;

- knowledge of educators along with students and regular training;

- establishing an effective cooperation mechanism between the family, educational institutions and the neighborhood, as well as mass media and other social structures;

- spiritual education is based on the principles of gradual development and continuity.

The concept envisages a new, systematic approach to education, the full use of the pedagogical capabilities of the family, preschool and general secondary education institutions in the guaranteed design and teaching of basic qualities, and raising scientific-methodical cooperation between them to a new level. In the concept of continuous spiritual education, education should

not become an additional burden - a second-class work, which is carried out during free time from education, education has become a continuous process in the past periods, and the pedagogical culture of the society has decreased, preschool education, school pedagogues, parents it is noted that the pedagogical and psychological knowledge of mothers does not meet the requirements of the time. The most common of the mistakes made as a result of this is that oral education continues, parents, preschool educators, school teachers teach children loyalty to the Motherland, responsibility, entrepreneurship and other qualities become theoretical information and do not become children's habits, good thoughts, it is noted that as a result of the lack of good words and good deeds, there is a discrepancy between the words of young people about loyalty to the Motherland, responsibility, entrepreneurship, and kindness and their age-appropriate actions.

Today's era requires the creation of a modern and rational system in the field of education in the context of large-scale reforms implemented in our country. The most important tasks to be performed in this regard are the need to update teaching methods, educational standards, textbooks and training manuals, to use advanced foreign experiences in imparting knowledge, and to observe national traditions and values in education. Especially in the "Concept of Continuous Spiritual Education" special attention is paid to legal pedagogical opportunities in education. In Uzbekistan, the work on the scientific and technological reform of youth education on a modern basis calls for its formation based on scientifically based basic competencies and qualities based on today's needs. A new, systematic approach to education, to fully reveal the socio-pedagogical possibilities of the family, preschool education, general secondary, secondary special vocational, higher educational institutions, neighborhoods in the guaranteed formation of basic qualities in a child, and scientific-methodical unity among them to a new level. requires lifting. Loyalty to the motherland, duty and responsibility, initiative and other qualities remain as theoretical concepts in the minds of young people, but they do not become practical habits in their nature. As a result, there is a discrepancy between their words about these qualities and their actions, which causes a number of problems for young men and women who enter independent life every year to find their place in life. It can be observed that the lack of formation of high goals, self-mobilization to study, insufficient development of the qualities of will, perseverance, perseverance, and movement in some students-young people also harms the quality of education.

The concept calls for a new, systematic approach to education, to fully reveal the socio-pedagogical possibilities of the family, pre-school education, general secondary, secondary special vocational, higher educational institutions, neighborhoods in the guaranteed formation of basic qualities in a child, and among them scientific-methodical sets the highest goal of raising unity to a new level. As a result, the successful implementation of the concept shows that further development of the spiritual education system is a promising task. The importance of continuous spiritual education is that educational education in kindergartens, schools, lyceums, colleges, technical schools and higher education institutions is combined with spiritual education in the family. This is the most important task within the scope of the Strategy of Actions implemented in Uzbekistan. Based on the above points, it can be said that the family occupies an important place in the life of every person. Its development in all directions depends, first of all, on the personality of parents, and also on other family members. There is no need to explain who the children in the family will be, especially if our women are literate and well-educated in the family. Because any human child first begins to form mentally and physically in the mother's womb. Then he grows up with his father and other relatives. Special attention should be paid to the fact that young people

join various negative groups. To prevent such situations, creating a healthy psychological climate in the family, mutual trust in the relations of family members and their treatment, mutual respect will protect our children from joining various negative groups in the family. Also, parents' participation of their children in various clubs, participation in sports, not allowing them to spend their time in vain, and, if necessary, working in cooperation with the school community and internal affairs departments, protect minors from crimes.

Therefore, the education of young people in the family requires continuity and systematic continuation of traditions such as family duty, respect, loyalty, and honor, which exist in the family and in everyday life, from generation to generation. Also, a person brought up in a healthy family should always strive to build a fair society and develop it, to live in peace and harmony.

On December 27, 2019, our President said, "We will definitely build a new Uzbekistan together with the youth. 2020 will be the year of a fundamental turning point in the youth policy"[4], which also shows the perspective of the reforms being implemented in this regard.

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